

Peresupposition of Addressings in the Works of Tokhir Malik

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Abstract

This article discusses the Uzbek word for addressing, its place in speech, its use, and the views of linguists on the subject. The role of peresupposition in addressing is studied and illustrated by the work of Tahir Malik.

Keywords: grammatical category, addressing, place of addressing, types of addressing, peresupposition, parts of speech.

Numerous studies on the study of grammatical categories, such as addressing, introduction words, have been done in Uzbek linguistics. The 1940 textbook "Grammar of the Uzbek Language" by A. Gulomov provides a visual illustration of this. Addressing, introduction words, and the words yes and no at the beginning of the phrase are examples of terms in this book that are not technically related to parts of speech. The following is how the author of this book discusses the particulars of addressing:

1. Addressing refers to the person, the subject, to whom the speaker's speech is directed.
2. Incentives include people's names, kinship names, age-appropriate names, and names that represent status and practice.
3. The addressing may have its own identifier. This is called diffuse addressing" [Gulomov, 1940: 63].

As an example of the above description, we can cite the following passage from Tahir Malik's *Shaytanat*:

- ***Can't the tomb be opened, shrouded, and reburied?***// – *No need for that, bo'tam (my child). First of all, it is better not to disturb the dead. (SH, II, p.291).*

We know that addressing are free in the sentence, that is, they can occur at the beginning, middle and end of the sentence. The role of the addressing depends on its semantic function, stylistic structure, and most importantly, the structure and meaning of the sentence. Writers use motivation in their work in three ways: prepositive, interpositive, and postpositive [Juraboyeva K. 2011: 14.] We will consider each of them separately:

In the prepositive case, that is, when addressing comes at the beginning of a sentence, the speaker's goal is to get the listener's attention, and the thought is directed to a specific addressee: – *He came across to Imomaliyev and stopped in the hallway. – Comrade Major, there was a girl among them. She stood aside. (AB, p.10).*

The impulse at the addressing of a sentence is separated more strongly than the addressing at the other end, where there is always a separating pause. This is also the reason why the proper noun addressing often appears at the beginning of a sentence.

In the interpositive case, when the motivation comes in the middle of the speech, it is important for the speaker not to distract the listener, but to keep in touch with him. The addressing in the middle is weaker and the pause is weaker. The middle addressing, however, is often pronounced as quickly as the introductory word, as well as in a lower tone. While the addressing at the beginning of a sentence is characterized by the function of a stimulus, the stimuli in the middle and at the end of a sentence often serve to express emotionality, modality - the speaker's attitude to the interlocutor, rather than the function of the stimulus: – *Don't blame my sister, brother, we didn't mean to sit down, 'said the customer, walking towards the round table. (T, p.46).*

In the postpositive state, that is, at the end of a sentence, the thought is expressed first, and then the listener's attention is drawn. Communication between listener and speaker is extremely weak in this case. In the end, the words that come out of the addressings are often more concise than the content: – *Will these be fair, son? Asked the old woman in an uncertain tone. (VO, p.10.).*

In linguistics, there is the term peresupposition, which refers to the concepts of inter knowledge, inter meaning (real meaning). The term refers to a hidden meaning that is not directly expressed in the sentence. Grammatical forms in which some words in a simple sentence are not syntactically related to parts of speech can also express a special presupposition and complicate the simple sentence. In this case, the proposition expressed in some word or grammatical form has its own concise form. The presupposition helps to make it clear to the communicators. That is why the presupposition of speech has been growing in Uzbek linguistics lately.

Peresupposition is the contextual meaning of a sentence, which is inextricably linked to the semantic aspect of syntactic constructions and is itself part of pragmatics. The syntactic description of any sentence is based on a certain amount of presupposition, because presupposition is a condition of the speech process that is not related to it, "strange speech" and forms its basis. [Makhmudov N. 1986: 6.]

Taking into account that peresupposition can also be given by some words in a simple sentence, we can say that addressing also represent a specific presupposition [Nurmonov A. 1976: 6.]

The peresupposition of an addressed sentence is its internal text, which is specific to the idea being expressed. Language communication is a moving system of interconnected factors of objective and subjective nature, which occurs in human communication. It also determines the status and character of the communicators in the communication process.

The most important feature of addressing is the peresupposition of the speaker's various subjective attitudes toward the listener. Any addressing will have a presupposition to the listener that expresses a state of mind, such as emphasis, protest, warning, satisfaction, caress, anger, as well as additional information about the quality characteristics of the addressee. For example: – *Be careful, boy, I'm going to crush your jaw (SH, II, 104).* To understand the real meaning of the child's addressing in the example, we need to know the age between the speaker and the listener. It is taken from Khaidar's speech in the play, and the listener is Makhmud. Khaydar is only 3-4 years older than Makhmud.

Mahmoud is not a child as he says, on the contrary, he has a child, an adult. Khaidar's reference to "child" means "I am older and stronger than you, and you are still a child". Or consider another example: – *My dear emir, give me a spoonful of my blood, you have been misinformed. (SH, II, 129-b)*. It is through the Emir's addressing that the listener's position takes precedence over the speaker's.

It can be divided into two depending on the application of the addressing:

1. Contact a familiar addressee.
2. Contact an unknown or confused addressee.

Familiar names (anthroponyms), kinship terms, the character of the addressee, and descriptive descriptions (descriptive words) are used as a means of addressing in the familiar presupposition to the listener. For example: – *Fazli, run away, God has struck me.*

... *No more seats, Fazli. Don't spend a penny on me anymore" (SH, p.16).*

In the unfamiliar group of addressees, descriptions are used to describe proper nouns, the age, appearance, location, etc. of the person to whom the speech is addressed. In Uzbek, when referring to an unfamiliar addressee, the stimuli of brother-in-law, uncle, aunt, daughter-in-law, good girl, boyfriend, sister are often used, and the addressee corresponding to these words is an adult stranger: brother-in-law; an older stranger, a middle-aged stranger, a peer, or a younger girl, a young, older or younger woman also reflects the presupposition of a respectful or abusive (positive or negative) attitude, depending on the situation. Addressings applied to a familiar or unfamiliar addressee reflect the presupposition that communication (appeal) is divided into different areas. For example:

➤ *I'm astonished, yigitning guli (best of the boys)! – said Storm, applauding him. – Shark, you see, a purebred man is so brave. (T, p.67).*

They can be divided into 4 groups:

- 1) Administrative and legal incentives: *by first, last name, patronymic, colleague, master, teacher, comrade, friend, or by quoting the words respectable, dear, esteemed before these words;*
- 2) Socio-vital addressing: *aunt, uncle, cousin, daughter-in-law, grandfather, friend, brother, or before these words the words respectful, esteemed 'by adding jon or khon;*
- 3) Socio-cultural motivations: *mother, father, brother, aunt, sister, friend;*
- 4) Addressing related to professions: *such as peasant, teacher, tutor, otinoya, farmer.*

We know that addressing is pronounced with a separate call, an intonation of appeal. But this intonation comes at different levels. The level of the intonation of the addressing depends on the meaning expressed by the addressing, the nature, the composition, the place of the main sentence, and finally, the intention of the speaker to express a particular content. For this reason, although the addressing is in the same place in the works of the artist, it is said with different intonation according to the nature of the speech. They are:

1. In declarative sentence - with low intonation:

➤ *I grew up an orphan myself, sister" she cried. (Z. p.42).*

2. In exclamatory sentence - with strong intonation:

➤ *Animal, go away! said Kesakpolvon. (Sh. IV. P.12)*

3. In interrogative sentences, a long pause is given after an addressing that has a special logical emphasis:

➤ My child, my child, I never believed ... but why did it happen? (VO. P.28).

4. The command is said in sentences with a strong intonation:

➤ Uncle, four beers are a lot for you, sell me three, 'he said, handing over three rubles. (AB. P.19).

In particular, the addressing in which the word is spread or the exclamation point is quite different in terms of intonation. At the same time, addressing which has a strong emotional meaning and a logical emphasis, is said with a distinct intonation that separates it from the parts of speech, regardless of where the sentence comes from:

➤ Wow, Bek aka, is that you?" She greeted him and went to ask how he was. (Sh. V. p.54).

During the speech, the speaker may want to draw the listener's attention to that information during the presentation of a certain reality, or in addition to this information, he may want to express his certain subjective attitude to the listener. Such a relationship is called an appealing relationship, and this relationship is created by addressing. The appealing approach complicates the existing speech content. Subjective content is added to the objective content, the appealing attitude of the speaker. For example:

➤ Ha, azizlar, halol yashagan odam jannatga hisobsiz kiradi. (Z. 114-b). Ushbu gapda ko'rib turganingizdek, " jannatga hisobsiz kirish uchun halol yashaylik" degan undash mazmuni yotadi.

It should be noted that in the Uzbek language, many studies are being created on the role and use of addressing and its presupposition. As we saw above, their role in syntax is broad. We were especially convinced that the role of addressing in the works of Tokhir Malik is unpopular. Based on the works of art, we have studied the different meanings of the addressing used in the author's speech on the basis of scientific and well-founded theoretical opinions of linguists.

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